

APPLICABILITY AND RELEVANCE OF SCIENCE LEARNING COMPETENCIES TOWARD WORK IMMERSION OF GRADE 12 STEM STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study was focused on the applicability and relevance of science learning competencies toward work immersion of Batangas City and Area II of Batangas Province, Division of Batangas, Grade 12 STEM students with an end view of proposing science competency assessment tool to assess their competencies necessary toward work immersion. Relevantly, this aimed to assess the science competencies of STEM students relative to technical, behavioral, communicative and leadership. Also, it assessed the extent of the development of science competencies in the terms of objectives, instructional strategies, learning resources and evaluative measures. Furthermore, in this study the industry personnel assessed the applicability and relevance of science competencies in work immersion. The descriptive method of research was employed by means of questionnaire, FGD and random interview. Based on the result, it was found that much were focused on leadership and communicative competencies of Grade 12 STEM students as shown by the composite mean of 3.43 and 3.33 respectively; hence there was a need for the facilitator of learning to strengthen the students' technical and behavioral competencies, the aforesaid competencies were most required in the workplace. Much of the science competencies of Grade 12 STEM students are relative to communicative and leadership, hence there is a need for the facilitator of learning to strengthen the students' technical and behavioral competencies which were found the most required competencies in the workplace.

Keywords: Science learning competencies, acquired competencies, work immersion, STEM, competency assessment tool, Batangas Province, Philippines

